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Critical Discourse Analysis of the English Text- *Slaughterhouse-five* and its Persian Translation through Ideological Approach

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ABSTRACT

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), with particular emphasis on the framework of Fairclough (1989), has been considered as an effective tool of investigation in the current study. Investigating the relationship between language and ideology, involved in translation, is an important goal in this research to uncover the visibility and invisibility of ideological assumptions as conscious manipulation or unconscious manipulation in both source text and target text. The text *Slaughterhouse-five*, written in English by Kurt Vonnegut, and its corresponding version in Persian have been considered as the corpus in this study. Both qualitative phase and quantitative phase were investigated in nine discursive elements at Fairclough's (1989) three dimensional model. In a qualitative phase, a detailed comparative study was conducted. While, in quantitative phase, two categories of statistical data were computed; the percentage and frequencies of discursive elements as well as statistical data about conscious or unconscious manipulation. The researchers have benefited by a rater's confirmation to assert the reliability result of the study, who verified data collection and analysis procedure. The findings revealed that significant deviations in discursive elements had been done by the translator consciously or unconsciously. The findings also showed that many deviations in the translated version were not only arbitrary, but also ideologically encoded in the text, with specific purposes and functions.

Keywords: Ideology; Conscious manipulation; Unconscious manipulation; Discursive element; Discourse.

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1. Introduction

For a long time, translation critics have been evaluating and criticizing translations in terms of readability, naturalness, accuracy, appropriateness, and equivalence and so on. Because of the growing globalization in recent decades, the need for translation also has increased. Consequently translation critics have altered their view points to different extra linguistic subjects such as ideology, power abuse, culture and manipulation. Therefore, text does not convey meaning only through linguistic features but it is generated and realized by certain ideologies (Fairclough, 1989). Lefever (1992), one of the representatives in the manipulation school, believes that translation is the rewriting of source text which are manipulated by ideology. In this case, Lefever (1992) has explained that the most important extra linguistic consideration is the ideological one, which refers to the translator's ideology, or the ideology imposed upon the translator by patronage.

Recently, ideological issue in translations and the effect of ideological translations on the target readership has been discussed a lot. Regarding translation and ideology, Fairclough (2004) has mentioned that "Translated texts are available and reliable sources for research to emerge ideology and to explore social and political conditions in a given society at a given time". (P: 104). The ideology underlying a text could be found and understood by critical discourse analysis (CDA). In other words, CDA tries to analyze the translated texts accurately to see how much of the original writer's ideology is visible in the translation and to what extent cultural values affect this process.

In CDA, the scholars try to study the existing influences of the dominant power relations and authorities on discourse (Widdowson, 1997) because they believe that

the translators' ideology is integrated in every word they choose through translation process (Tory, 2006). Identifying discourse to discover ideology is a crucial element for translators to have a proper translation and to convey the proper message that the original text intends to give. So, a variety of strategies are applied by translators to have a proper translation and manipulate a text ideologically.

Translators and translation students must be aware that communicating information is not the only responsibility of the language and rewriting the original message is not the only goal of translators. According to Baker (2006), the translators and interpreters are responsible for being faithful to the values of their society too. Therefore, translation critics, by using critical discourse analysis, try to throw the light on the path of translation process to discourse ideologies underlying a text and different approaches to talking and thinking.

Considering the emergence of the concept of text manipulation in the translation studies, and spreading the concept of ideology in the academic studies, the current study aims to investigate the extent that a Persian translator, consciously or unconsciously, and based on ideology, manipulates a text through translation process and the amount of frequencies and percentages in every discursive elements that has been applied consciously or unconsciously. To this end the following research question are addressed:

- 1- What are the frequencies and percentages of the discursive elements in the translated version of the book *slaughterhouse-five* by Kurt Vonnegut translated by Ali Asghar Bahrami based on Fairclough (1989) CDA model?
- 2- What are the frequencies and percentage of conscious or unconscious

ideological manipulation of the discursive patterns?

2. Literature Review

Critical Discourse Analysis has been considered as an effective school that offers materials to investigate different concepts such as ideology and manipulation in translation (Fairclough, 1997). In this respect, a multitude number of studies have been conducted on the way the translators ideologically manipulate a text consciously or unconsciously. In this regard, Sai-Hua Kuo and Mari Nakamura (2005) performed a research based on CDA approach. They analyzed and discussed the news report related to Taiwan's first lady Wu Shu-chen's interview with the media which appeared in two ideologically opposed newspapers. Both news articles are translated from an identical English text. However, based on different comparisons, they found that noticeable changes were made by the two translated Chinese versions which are not arbitrary, but rather are ideologically motivated. That is, they reflected and constructed the underlying opposed ideologies between the two newspapers.

Another study conducted in the realm of ideological manipulation is by Mohammad Hossein Keshavarz & Leila Alimadadi Zonoozi (2011). This CDA approached research was conducted on the scope of political text and was based on theories of Fairclough (1989), Van Dijk (2004) and Farahzad (2007). Three English political books, alongside their corresponding translations in Persian, were critically analyzed both at micro and macro levels. At micro-level, lexical features based on Van Dijk's model (2004) and grammatical features based on Fairclough's (1989) framework were analyzed. At macro-level, semiotic features based on Farahzad (2007) model were analyzed. The results showed

that translators make use of certain grammatical and lexical strategies for the sake of ideological ploy. That is, all the lexical and grammatical deviations used by the Persian translators were in the employment of self (i.e., Iranian) interests. Also the analysis of macro-features revealed the translators' ideological trends and judgments toward the source texts.

In this regard, Katayoon Afzali, (2013) performed a research on translation and manipulation. In this research, her aim was to investigate how and to what extent Iranian translation students are familiar with the changes that the meanings of ethics and manipulation have undergone in translation studies. The findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference across two types of translations. Furthermore, it was revealed that lexicality is the most frequent discursive structure used by the students to show their ideology in translation.

As mentioned above a multitude number of studies have focused on the CDA to reveal the prevailing ideology reflected in translation consciously or unconsciously. Those research attempted to reveal the relation of discourse and ideology. Therefore, the current study, by using critical discourse analysis, aims to investigate the relationship between language and ideology involved in translation to uncover the underlying ideological assumptions invisible in English text and its corresponding Persian text based on Fairclough's (1989) model; and consequently, ascertain whether or not translators' ideologies are imposed in their translations as conscious manipulation or unconscious manipulation.

3. Methodology

3.1 Material

The selected text for this study was *Slaughterhouse-five* or *The Children's Crusade* by Kurt Vonnegut which was

published in 1972 by Boston independent publisher, Seymour Lawrence. This ninety seven-page novel is something beyond active mind of the author. It is based on the author's experience during World War II which is to some extent similar to Iranians' experience during imposed war by Iraq in 1980. Its corresponding version was translated in Persian by Ali Asghar Bahrami, in 2004 and published by Morvarid Press, in Tehran. This book is a sociopolitical novel. Sociopolitical texts are instances of text where ideology, in its purest or crudest form, could be manifested as the core of the translation process. Since the aim of the study was to detect translator's ideological manipulation, a sociopolitical novel were selected to explore the amount of the lexical and grammatical deviations that have been performed in the translation process to reflect ideology as conscious or unconscious manipulation.

3.2 Procedure

The present study focused on contrasting the source text with its target text to find the ideological adjustment, and the translator's manipulation through them, based on Fairclough's model (1989). Fairclough (1989) has illustrated a three-dimensional framework in which the connection between text and social practice is mediated by discourse practice. Correspondingly, "there is a three-stage method of discourse analysis which includes description of the text (lexically and grammatically), interpretation of the relationship between the discursive processes and the text, and explanation of the relationship between the discursive processes and the social processes" (Fairclough, 1995, P: 97). Among the elements proposed by Fairclough, Lexicalization, Pattern of Transitivity, Active and Passive voice, Nominalization, Mode, Modality, Thematic Structure, Information Focus, Cohesive Device were focused in this study.

Lexicalization refers to choosing one word rather than another. Patterns of transitivity refers to finding transitive verbs replacing with intransitive ones or vice versa. Active and passive voice refers to changing an active sentence to a passive one or vice versa. Nominalization refers to changing a phrase to a noun. Mode means searching in which mode the sentences had been written, declarative, grammatical question or imperative. Modality can show the likelihood of the occurrence of an action (Auxiliary verbs, Simple present verbs as truth proposition, and intermediate possibilities such as probability and possibility). Thematic structure relates to the text's higher-level of organizational features containing the exact concept of the text. The information focus relates to the formal organizational properties of the whole texts. Cohesive devices focus upon logical connectors.

To analyze the translation, first, the differences between the source-text and target-text were found and analyzed at description level. In description level, lexical items, grammatical choices and choices of translation strategies were respectively tabulated. At the second level of the analysis, the interpretation of the collected data was conducted. And the third level was allocated to the explanation of the data to find the relationship between discourse and social and cultural reality. To increase the reliability of the conclusion and to make the interpretation objective as much as possible, all data were analyzed both qualitatively and quantitatively. For qualitative analysis, some political and sociopolitical loaded items (discursive elements) in both texts were collected; then classified as conscious or unconscious manipulation. For quantitative analysis, not only the frequency and percentage of discursive elements but also the translator's conscious and unconscious

manipulation based on ideology were computed.

4. Data Analysis and Findings

Both the English version of the book and its Persian translation were compared based on CDA modal of Fairclough (1989). One hundred discursive elements were tabulated. First, the differences between the source-text and target-text were found and analyzed at description level (lexical items, grammatical choices and choices of translation strategies). At the second level, the interpretation of the collected data was conducted. And the third level was allocated to the explanation of the data to find the relationship between discourse and social and cultural reality. The frequency and percentages of the nine discursive elements that mentioned before were presented in table 1 respectively.

Figure 1: The Percentage of Discursive Elements

In order to facilitate the comparison of discursive elements in two texts, figure 1 shows the frequency and percentage of these discursive elements in the form of a bar graph. The classification of the translator's manipulation analyzed based on Kramina (2004); "the manipulation arising due to ideological, economic, and cultural considerations is the conscious one and the manipulation ascribed to the features of human psychology and ignorance is considered as the unconscious one" (P: 1). The frequency and percentages of the translator's conscious or unconscious

manipulation were presented in table 2 respectively.

In order to facilitate the comparison of discursive elements, based on the translator's conscious manipulation in two texts, figure 2 shows the frequency and percentage of these discursive elements in the form of bar graph.

Figure 2: The Percentage of Conscious Manipulation

In order to facilitate the comparison of discursive elements based on the translator's unconscious manipulation in two texts, figure 3 shows the frequency and percentage of these discursive elements in the form of bar graph.

Figure 3: The Percentage of Unconscious Manipulation

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The result showed that lexicalization has the highest rate of deviation than other discursive elements; while Pattern of Transitivity has the lowest rate. The investigation of the translator's conscious and unconscious manipulations indicated that

the highest rate of frequency in conscious manipulation is allocated to lexicalization while, the lowest rate is allocated to cohesive devices. The highest rate of frequency in unconscious manipulation is allocated to cohesive devices and the lowest rate is allocated to lexicalization. Generally, the frequency of the translator's conscious manipulation is (53 %) and the frequency of the translator's unconscious manipulation is (47 %). It must be mentioned that, the translator's conscious manipulation in the source text takes place in lexical choices more than the grammatical choices. So, a great number of deviations in grammatical elements are done unconsciously.

As data shows, the highest rate belongs to the lexicalization and modality which are 19 % and 17 % alternatively. It shows that translator, by use of modality as a grammatical element, insists on prevailing ideology in target culture. According to Fairclough (1989), modality consists of three parts: simple tense to show exact idea, auxiliary verb to indicate the degree of necessity and adverb to show the mood of events. All of these subcategories insisted on prevailing ideology in a text. Similarly, the translator prefers lexicalization as a crucial element to reflect intended ideology to the target reader as Fairclough (1989) mentioned, terminology is likely to lend legitimacy to the facts and their underlying power relations. On the other hand, the most frequent percentage of translator's conscious manipulation belongs to lexicalization which is 89.42 %. It seems that by using lexicalization elements, the translator attempted to give priority to intended ideology through the translation process because this discursive element contains ideological loaded items that have direct relation with the main concepts in the text as well as prevailing ideology. The most frequency percentage of translator's

unconscious manipulation belongs to cohesive device (100%). It seems that translator has made effort to talk mostly around the topic of the book and increase the semantic load of many lexical items for the benefit of the prevailing ideology.

The research aimed to show how translators' political ideologies are presented in translations and what strategies are used by them to represent their ideas. The finding of the current study indicates a number of recommendations for practice. These findings are expected to be beneficial for undergraduate student of translation studies, translators, translation workshops and translation teachers. It is also beneficial for the translation course instructors to provide some practical guidelines for their students.

Translation plays a quite significant role in communicating and exchanging social, cultural and political information. Translation of political concepts is a fundamental problematic area in translation study and practice as translator attempts to keep the original item in order not to lose the local color of the text, and at the same time to be in agreement with the dominated policy in the target society. The most important limitation imposed on the choice of the translator is the interference of the extra-linguistic factors such as ideology. The prevailing ideology in a society may be reflected in translation consciously or unconsciously through the lexicalization or grammatical choices. The meaning of every lexical item consists of its meaning components and any changes in these components may lead to an ideological alteration. Similarly, the function of every grammatical choice as a communication device is determined by its context and any changes in this context may lead to an ideological alteration too. Therefore, it is important for translators and translation students to be familiar with the changes that

lexical and grammatical items have undergone in translation process.

According to Fairclough (1995), there are three dimensions in CDA: text, interaction, and social context. Fairclough (1995) argued that analyzing a text without context (in isolation) is impossible. The first dimension sees discourse as text and comprises the linguistic features (vocabulary and grammar) and organization of discourse (cohesion and text structure). The second dimension sees discourse as discursive practice that refers to rules, norms, and mental models of socially accepted behavior, reflected in text production and interpretation. Fairclough's third dimension sees discourse as social practice that pivots around the larger social context. Concept of ideology is the central at this stage. Fairclough (1992) maintained that ideology is located both in the structure of discourse and in the discourse practices.

Certain aspects of this study need through investigation. First, critical discourse analysis covers different concepts such as power, ideology, gender etc. however, the present study covered ideological aspect only. Other concepts can be studied by CDA models. Second, the researchers have worked on a sociopolitical text and have tried to find conscious manipulation in translation based on translator's ideology. Other kinds of texts can be studied by CDA models. Third, this study has used Fairclough model of CDA. However, there are different CDA models which can be used to cast any of the above mentioned studies. Fourth, this research is confined to only one English sociopolitical novel; however other genre could be investigated. Fifth, among different elements proposed by Fairclough (1989), nine discursive elements were identified and used to analyze in this study. Other studies could focus on identifying other discursive elements and focus.

The revealing results of the translator's conscious and unconscious manipulation indicates that the highest rate of frequency in conscious manipulation is allocated to lexicalization and the lowest rate allocated to cohesive devices. On the other hand, the highest rate of frequency in unconscious manipulation is allocated to cohesive devices and the lowest rate is allocated to lexicalization. It appears that the translator's conscious manipulation in the source text takes place in the lexical choices more than the grammatical choices. So a great number of deviations in grammatical elements are done unconsciously.

About the Authors

Neda Heidari Moghadam holds a M.A degree in English Translation as a foreign language. Her major area of interest includes translation, contrastive analysis and discourse analysis.

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Appendices:

Table: 1 The Frequencies and Percentages of each Discursive Element

No.	Discursive Element	Frequency	Percentage
1	Lexicalization	19	19 %
2	Pattern of Transitivity	4	4 %
3	Active and Passive	16	16 %
4	Nominalization	11	11 %
5	Mode	6	6 %
6	Modality	17	17 %
7	Thematic structure	8	8 %
8	Information	10	10 %
9	Cohesion devices	9	9 %

Table: 2 The Frequencies and Percentages of Conscious and Unconscious Manipulations

No	Discursive Elements		Frequency	Percentage
1	Lexicalization	consciously	17	89.42 %
		unconsciously	2	10.52 %
2	Pattern of Transitivity	consciously	1	25 %
		unconsciously	3	75 %
3	Active and Passive	consciously	3	18.75 %
		unconsciously	13	81.25 %
4	Nominalization	consciously	5	45 %
		unconsciously	6	54 %
5	Mood	consciously	4	66.4 %
		unconsciously	2	33.2 %
6	Modality	consciously	12	70.56 %
		unconsciously	5	29.4 %
7	Thematic Structure	consciously	4	50%
		unconsciously	4	50%
8	Information focus	consciously	7	70 %
		unconsciously	3	30 %
9	Cohesive Devices	consciously	0	0%
		unconsciously	9	100%

References

Afzali, K. (2013). The Translator's Agency and the Ideological Manipulation in Translation: the Case of Political Texts in Translation Classrooms in Iran. *International Journal of English Language and translation Studied* 1(2).

Baker, M. (2006). *Translation and conflict: A narrative account*, London: Routledge.

Fairclough, N. (1989). *Language and power*. London: Longman.

Fairclough, N. (1995). *Critical discourse analysis: The critical study of language*. Harlow: Longman.

Fairclough, N. (2004). *Critical Discourse Analysis in Researching Language in the New Capitalism*. London: Continuum.

Keshavarz, M.H., & Alimadadi, L. (2011). Manipulation of Ideology in Translation of Political Texts: A Critical Discourse Analysis Perspective. *Journal of language and translation, Vol: 2, Num: 1*

Kramina, A. (2004). Translation as Manipulation: Causes and Consequences, Opinions and Attitudes. *Journal of Kalbu Studijos, 1648-2824*

Lefever, A. (1992). *Translation/History/Culture*. London and New York: Routledge.

Kuo, S. & Nakamura, M. (2004). *Translation or transformation? A case study of language and ideology in the Taiwanese press*. Retrieved from: <http://www.sagepublications.com>

Wodak, R. (2001). *What CDA is about: A summary of its history, important concepts and its developments*. London: Sage Publications.

Wodak, R. (2000). *Recontextualisation and the transformation of meaning: a critical discourse analysis of decision making in EU-meetings about employment policies*. Harlow: Pearson Education.

Wodak, R., & Meyer, M. (2001). *Method of Critical Discourse Analysis*. London: Thousand Oaks, New Delhi.